

Research Article

Fear of Overwatering or Underwatering? Solve it with Autowater

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Abstract: *In today's fast-paced world, people often lack the time to water and monitor their plants regularly. However, ensuring plants receive sufficient water is essential for their growth and health. To address this challenge while promoting environmental sustainability, we present the Auto Waterer, an innovative, eco-friendly watering system designed using recyclable materials. The Auto Waterer operates without the need for electricity or constant human supervision, embodying the principles of the "Go Green" concept. Today, automatic watering systems with automated features that depend on direct electricity or renewable energy such as solar energy conversion have been developed. However, most of them are highly priced to get and install. Alternatively, auto waterer using rainwater is more eco-friendly. Therefore, the proposed Auto Waterer was an initiative to overcome this problem. Leveraging the principles of physics, specifically the Law of Gravity, the system utilizes collected rainwater stored in a tank. Gravity enables the water to flow efficiently to the plants. A specially designed cap with an adjustable nozzle ensures precise control over the water flow, allowing for an ideal drip rate. In this innovation, two designs of Auto Waterer were developed with different structures and functions each. Design A was built with three drains that function to collect and flow rainwater into the auto waterer tank. In contrast, Design B consists of two water tanks that help to store more rainwater. This innovation eliminates concerns about overwatering or underwatering, offering a reliable and sustainable solution for plant care. The Auto Waterer not only simplifies plant maintenance but also contributes to conserving natural resources and protecting Mother Earth. Lastly, this innovation was proposed to benefit the agriculture industry.*

Keywords: Auto waterer; Green concept; Sustainable; Environmentally friendly; Portable.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The study proposes a new auto-watering system meant to overcome common difficulties faced by gardeners and farmers, such as limited time and the high cost of automated systems. Unlike existing solar-powered systems that require electricity (Eragamreddy & Sree, 2017), the suggested system prioritizes sustainability by depending on rainfall and gravity for operation. It creates a simple and cost-effective design using recyclable materials such as plastic bottles, straws, and cotton, solving disadvantages such as installation difficulty, high costs, and sensor errors. This eco-friendly solution promotes the "Go Green" , the study of thought by removing the need for energy, while also maintaining healthy plant development through controlled water distribution utilizing modified nozzles.

The study analyzed two auto-watering system designs on *Capsicum Chinense* (Habanero pepper) plants, optimizing nozzle adjustments to get the ideal water drip rate. This gravity-fed system is complemented by a rainwater collection technology to ensure optimal water storage and utilization. The study highlights the environmental and cost benefits of this technique over solar-powered alternatives, which are more expensive and less effective in locations with variable sunlight (Chadly et al., 2024; IRENA, 2023). China, for example, leads in solar PV production, however the resources necessary for solar panel manufacturing increase costs and have an environmental impact (Pourasl, Barenji, & Khojastehnezhad, 2023). This innovative system, which uses gravity and recyclable materials, provides a sustainable, user-friendly irrigation solution while encouraging sustainable practices in agriculture and gardening.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

For Design A, it was designed using 1.5L plastic water bottle with cap, cotton, gauze, hard straw, waterproof cardboard and flower hose for the auto waterer. Firstly, it started by making three square holes at the bottom of the 1.5L water for about 3 cm from its base. Aside from that, three cardboards were cut into 10 until 15 cm length and 6 cm width. Then, the cardboards were folded into a square drain with 10 to 15 cm length, 2 cm height and 2 cm width. Next, the three drain cardboard were secured with hot glue gun around it in a 30 position as shown in Figure 1. After that, a hard straw was cut with a length of 3 cm and was filled in with cotton with compatibility that was suitable for the water rate. A hole was made in the centre of the bottle cap and it was the same size as the hard straw. The hard straw was put inside the hole and was sealed using a hot glue gun. Meanwhile, the stand for auto waterer was made using wires, U shaped nails and cable ties. The stand holder was made with a 10 to 15 cm height, with the same diameter as the bottle while the feet was made with 23 to 25 cm height; using wire, cable ties and U-shaped nails as shown in Figure 1. Lastly, the stand was poked into the ground next to the plant and the auto waterer was placed in it.

For Design B, the materials needed were the same as the Design A but without using the waterproof cardboard and this design required two 1.5L water bottles. Firstly, one of the bottles was cut into three parts which are upper, middle and bottom. The bottle cap from the upper part was taken out so that it can act as a funnel for the rainwater flow. Moreover, a gauze was glued and sealed at the upper part but not the cap part to filter any substance from entering the auto waterer. Then, the upper part needs to be placed backwards into the bottom part as shown in Figure 1. After that, both of the bottles were glued together with each other, with the bottom part as the upper part of the auto waterer using a hot glue gun. Next, three holes were made at the bottom part of both bottles. A flower hose was cut into three pieces of 8 cm length and each of them were inserted at each hole by pairing with each

other. The flower hoses were sealed into the hole using a hot glue gun. After that, a hard straw was cut with a length of 3 cm and was filled in with cotton with compatibility that was suitable for the water rate. A hole was made in the centre of the bottle cap and it was the same size as the hard straw. The hard straw was put inside the hole and was sealed using a hot glue gun. Meanwhile, the stand for auto waterer was also the same as Design A which was made using wires, U shaped nails and cable ties. The stand holder was made with a 10 to 15 cm height, with the same diameter as the bottle while the feet was made with 23 to 25 cm height; using wire, cable ties and U-shaped nails as shown in Figure 1. Lastly, the stand was poked into the ground next to the plant and the auto waterer was placed in it.

Both designs were placed next to each other in an open area that was exposed with the rainwater for observation. The data of the observation for this study was taken every 2-3 days. The observations included the plant's growth, height and the conditions before and after the auto waterer applied.

Figure 1. The innovation designs.

3. FINDINGS

The result of this research shows that by using an auto waterer system with rainwater as the water source had improved the irrigation system effectiveness. It had reduced the water usage only by utilizing rainwater without depending on electricity. The system's potential for environmentally friendly water management can be seen by its capacity to collect water from rainwater and store them in the auto waterer for every rainfall. When compared to traditional methods, this system can reduce water waste while maintaining the soil moisture levels and proper soil hydration.

This research also discovered that it still could run without an external power source and emphasizing the "Go Green" concept. To lower operating cost, this innovation makes the system suitable for the areas with poor electrical access as it can be made using plastic materials and rainwater. It provides an economical and sustainable method for traditional or electrical irrigation techniques when it can benefit the uses in agriculture, especially to reduce cost of requirements.

Figure 2. The Auto Waterer installation

4. DISCUSSION

The primary purpose of the auto waterer that we design is the ability to store rainwater so that the plant receives enough water during drought season. Two designs for auto water have been developed. For design A, the rainwater is collected by the drain, while design B collects it directly into the auto waterer through a funnel made from plastic bottles. Both auto waterers were installed on the same plant species during testing. "Chilli Geronong," or its scientific name, *Capsicum Chinese*, is the plant that was chosen to test both designs of the auto water. Two auto-waterer designs were assessed under the same environmental conditions. As a result, both designs of auto waterers successfully maintain soil hydration, but their effects on the chilli plant differ. The contrasts are noticeable; design A produces more chilli, and the leaves are greener and grow taller than design B. This indicates that auto waterer design AA performs better because it can store more water at a faster rate. Even though Design B survived, the chilli plant that used Design A grew faster and healthier than the chilli plant Design B. However, both of the designs have drawbacks. If the drought persists, the irrigation system will be discontinued due to both of the tanks running dry. Therefore, the autowaterer cannot be used in areas where the weather is extremely dry. With this observation, we can conclude that Auto Waterer Design A is more efficient than Auto Waterer Design B.

5. CONCLUSION

In this Auto Waterer innovation, it demonstrates how the application of an automatic watering system based on the principles of the "Go Green" concept and physics can benefit more water sustainability and be environmentally friendly. This statement can be proven as no electricity and constant human supervision needed for them to operate. The components were made out of recycled materials, which lead to reducing the plastic waste. Meanwhile, the use of rainwater and its water retention feature can promote water-saving even during drastic weather change. Two designs were developed, where both designs applied the Gravity Law to flow the rainwater efficiently to the plant. Besides that, both designs were constructed with the top of the tank closed to minimize evaporation process during hot weather. The innovative nozzle modification attached with the bottle cap was used to control an ideal water drip for healthy plant growth. After taking into consideration, Design A is more effective to water the plant. Nevertheless, this Auto Waterer design is only applicable in tropical seasons which gives a limitation of the work because rainwater was used as the main water supply. However, this innovation still can be adapted in related countries. For instance, countries along the equatorial line which experience sunny and rainy days throughout the year can use this Auto Waterer innovation. Lastly, this Auto Waterer innovation benefits the users, economy and nature.

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